

The AquaPLAN Project: A Novel Approach to Studying the Combined Impacts of Light Pollution and Anthropogenic Noise on Aquatic Biodiversity

Elena Maggi¹, Martina Mulas¹, Francesco Caruso², Francesca Rossi³

DOI:

Abstract: The ADRISKY project addresses the growing challenge of light pollution and its detrimental effects on biodiversity and nocturnal habitats across the Adriatic–Ionian region. Bringing together nine partners and five associated partners from EU and IPA countries, the project leverages transnational cooperation to tackle an environmental threat that transcends administrative borders. ADRISKY’s overarching objective is to reduce light pollution and contribute to the long-term preservation of nocturnal ecosystems through an integrated, science-based, and participatory approach. The project develops seven Territorial Action Plans, providing strategic and technical guidance for the implementation of sustainable lighting practices and biodiversity protection measures. These plans outline tailored interventions for diverse pilot territories, enabling regional and local authorities to adopt durable solutions. Complementing this, ADRISKY produces a comprehensive Transferability and Implementation Toolkit, translating research findings, pilot actions, and best practices into accessible methodologies for policymakers, practitioners, researchers, and local communities. A key innovation of the project lies in the integration of citizen science, which broadens data collection, enhances public engagement, and strengthens the evidence base for policymaking. Through coordinated pilot actions, the project tests smart lighting technologies and nature-based solutions aimed at mitigating adverse impacts on nocturnal wildlife. At the policy level, ADRISKY formulates EU-oriented recommendations and a Provisional Action Plan for Nocturnal Habitat Conservation, fostering alignment with broader European environmental goals. By establishing the Adriatic–Ionian Light Pollution Mitigation Platform, the project ensures long-term cooperation, knowledge exchange, and capacity building across borders. ADRISKY ultimately contributes to a greener, more resilient region by promoting sustainable lighting, enhancing biodiversity conservation, and raising awareness of the importance of natural darkness.

Keywords: light pollution, noise pollution, interactive effects, AquaPLAN

Corresponding Author: elena.maggi@unipi.it

¹Dipartimento di Biologia, CoNISMa, University of Pisa, Italy

²Stazione Zoologica A. Dohrn, Naples, Italy

³Stazione Zoologica A. Dohrn, Genoa Marine Center, Italy